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CITY RENEWAL AND URBAN ARCHAEOLOGY

The morphological values of city traces

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The morphological values of city traces

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edited by

Bruna Di Palma
Francesca Coppolino
Valeria Defilippis
Salvatore Daniele Lombardi

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For any questions regarding figure references,
the individual authors are responsible.

Graphic layout design

Valeria Defilippis
Salvatore Daniele Lombardi
Oreste Lubrano
Giovangiuseppe Vannelli

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On the morphology of mediaeval market squares in Eastern Middle Europe

Martin Ebert

Institute of Building and Environmental Technology, Norwegian University of Life Sciences NMBU, Ås, Norway
Email: maeb@nmbu.no

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Abstract. Our knowledge of the spatial disposition of mediaeval market squares in Middle Europe has historically been based on cadastral maps of the 19th century. Recent archaeological excavations have added valuable new knowledge, casting new light on the size, function, layout, and diachronic changes throughout the last 800 years. Recent projects of renewing the surface of these market squares are a central element in the effort to revitalise small urban communities in rural areas in Mecklenburg and Lesser Pomerania. The study aims at a critical revision of established knowledge on the morphology of urban market squares in chartered towns planted in the 13th century east of the Elbe River. Recent archaeological research suggests that shape, size and function of market squares have undergone a great number of changes, contradicting the spatial disposition suggested in the cadastral maps of the 19th century. Special focus is given to the spatial relations between the market square, town hall and church; the morphology of urban space, neighbouring plots, streets and blocks; and building types related to market functions. Method: Four methods were used for this contribution: Excerpting a number of recent archaeological excavations, historical and interpretive research, logical argumentation based on analysis and synthesis, and the introduction of case studies. The study aims to collect and systematise knowledge of the spatial disposition of mediaeval market squares, their buildings and their relation to major urban features such as the parochial church and the town hall. This knowledge can serve as motives for future development based on typo-morphological approaches.

Figure 1. Urban layout of towns chartered during the early 13th century: Gadebusch, Grevesmühlen, Malchin, and Penzlin. Plot plans based on 2019 cadastral maps and 1857 cadastral map of Malchin, graphically processed by the author.

Introduction

Urban culture experienced an unprecedented expansion during the 12th and 13th centuries. A great number of urban communities developed either from existing rural settlements or were planted on behalf of the feudal lords. The urban revolution of the 12th and 13th centuries is documented in a great number of areas all over Europe; for example, England, Spain, France and Germany. This contribution focuses on urban settlements in Mecklenburg, a territory in the northern part of Germany. In its feudal realms, 34 towns were chartered during the course of the 13th century, creating the spatial disposition of its landscape still existing today.

The chartering of towns is inseparably related to the establishment of a network of local and regional markets, enabling trade and the specialisation of urban manufacturing and crafts (Schich 2000, XXXI). Therefore, the spatial disposition of the market square and its spatial relation to other major public buildings, such as the town hall and the parish church, is of great significance. Furthermore, changes in trade relations and economic circumstances created the need for spatial transformations of the market, documented in the archaeological records. A great number of excavations in Mecklenburg since 1990 have deepened our understanding of the spatial disposition in the marked squares of the region.

Geometric paradigms in medieval urban planning around 1200

The geometric analysis of urban layouts of settlements created around 1200 reveals a significant shift in planning paradigms of the age. Settlements chartered before the early 13th century often show irregular street geometries following the disposition of trade routes or terrain (Gadebusch 1190, Wittenburg 1200, Parchim 1225, Grevesmühlen (XXXX)). The urban layouts of the majority of later towns are signified by rectangular street layouts, suggesting a coordinated planning effort during the period of urban formation (Malchin 1215, Teterow, Ribnitz, ...) (Fig. 1). Similar changes in urban layouts can be, among others, observed in the French bastides in the aftermath of the Albigensian Crusade (1209-1229) (Barrett, 2016) or small towns in England (Boerefijn 2010, Dyer 2003 and Jervis 2025). Although this paradigm shift has to be seen as a universal European phenomenon, the cause for its similar introduction in different parts of Europe has been disputed. While some authors reason with Roman traditions or its apparent practicality (Boerefijn, 2000), some introduce the concept of 'model-towns' influencing others (Igel, 2013), while others argue for the change in the Christian view on the ideal city as a layout for prudent life (Conklin, 2019). Nevertheless, the consequences of this paradigm shift are clearly visible in the spatial disposition of chartered towns in 13th-century Mecklenburg (Fig. 2). It is therefore relevant to study the relation between the main urban institutions inside the walls, such as the market, town hall and church, in towns of different geometry.

Spatial relation between the market, town hall and church

The analysis of the spatial relation between the market square, town hall and the position of the church is struggling with methodological challenges. This is caused by the fact that modern cadastral maps do not necessarily reflect the spatial disposition of the mediaeval situation. The position of the town hall has in some cases changed up to several times during the last 800 years, or the spatial extension of the market does not reflect its correct historic layout. The results of archaeological excavations have therefore to be consulted to verify the mediaeval geometry.

It is apparent that market squares and churches have seldom visual or geometric relations in the irregular geometries of older towns in western parts of Mecklenburg. The urban plan of Grevesmühlen is a typical example of that. Its market square is situated at the intersection of main streets, entering the town through town gates. The urban development of Grevesmühlen started in the 1240s outside the bailiff's castle. St Nicolas Church, dated to 1230, is placed outside the grid of the main streets with no geometric relation to the market or the castle of the same age. The distribution can be described as rural, developing into an urban settlement during the course of the 13th century (Rehwaldt, 2014).

Figure 2. Urban geometry of 12th- and 13th-century towns in Mecklenburg. The year refers to the period of earliest formation, based on archaeological records, Ortsaktenarchiv of LAKD MV, and Westphal 2002.

The geometry of the rectangular plans shows a more direct link between the church and market square. In Malchin, planted around 1220 and chartered in 1236, the church/churchyard and market square share the same space. According to archaeological excavation, only minor buildings such as bread and meat banks separated marked a churchyard. Similar arrangements can be observed in towns like Neu Kalen (1280), Strelitz and Penzlin.

In a great number of towns the town hall is placed to separate the church and market square. The most prominent example of this disposition can be observed in Güstrow (ca. 1220), where a line of buildings, including the historic pharmacy and the town hall, separates the market square and the former churchyard around St Marien Church (Fig. 4). Similar dispositions can be found in a great number of towns (Fig. 3), including towns with non-rectangular geometry, like Wittenburg (ca 1200). In other cases a single line of plots separates the market and church, like in Ribnitz, Sternberg or Friedland. The single line consists preferably of public buildings like the latin school (Ribnitz) or the vicar's house (Friedland).

Finally, in a minor number of cases, the market and church are geometrically related but separated by one or more city blocks, which can be observed in Gnoien or Neu Brandenburg.

In summary, market squares and churches are occupying central positions in the majority of towns chartered in the 13th century. While market squares without exception are placed in the centre of the mediaeval urban tissue, the position of the church can vary, depending on topography and the origin (rural or urban) of the town's geometry.

Market square and town hall

The functionality of the town hall is inseparably linked to the existence of the market square (Meck-

category	principle	example	situation	comments	further examples
1	market and church occupy the same space 	The market of Penzlin appears today to be a cobbled square with no division between church yard and market. The town hall was destroyed in 1945 but has been documented by archaeological excavations.	Malchin 1220 Neu Kalen 1281 Strelitz ca. 1300		
2	town hall is situated as divider between market and church 	The old town hall of Wittenburg was removed in the 17th century. Today, the square therefore appears to include church and market.	Gadebusch (1200) Bützow (1220 ?) Güstrow (1220) Parchim (1220) Waren (?) Malchow (1230) Kröpelin (1240 ?) Sülze (1240 ?) Teterow (1270 ?)		
		Röbel (1235)		The modern town hall was erected 1673/1805 on the site of its mediaeval predecessor. Its exact position and its size is unknown. Today the town hall appears to be situated amidst a large urban square.	
3	market and church are divided by a single row of plots 	The baroque town hall at the centre of the square was destroyed in 1945. The single row of plots between market and churchyard of St Marien contains buildings belonging to the church. Map generated from the cadastral map of 1904.	Rostock A (1200) Ribnitz (1210) Sternberg (1250) Wesenberg (1260)		
4	market and church are divided by a city block 	Gnoien is a town with a large footprint, which was only partly settled during the Middle Age. The church was erected inside the walls but on the periphery of the settled town.	Neu Brandenburg (1240) Grabow (1250)		
5	market and church have no visual or geometric relation 	A number of towns with dislocated geometry between church and market are of rural origin (Grevesmühlen, Schwaan, Laage).	Wismar M (1220) Grevesmühlen (1240) Schwaan (1260?) Laage (1280?) Rostock M (1220) Rostock N (1240) Crivitz (?) Neustadt G (1240?) Woldegk (1250?)		

Figure 3. Geometric disposition of market square and church in selected towns in Mecklenburg. 1 = town hall, 2 = market square, 3 = churchyard. Illustration by the author.

seper, 1982, 59-60). In the towns of Mecklenburg, the town hall is therefore situated on or in the periphery of the square. Retracted town halls, which can be found in southern Germany, are not known. Historically, its first floor is related to commercial functions, sometimes creating covered arcades to place market stands (Dortmund, Stralsund). The second floor was reserved for representative functions and offices of merchants, while the cellars would be used as cold storage, additional sale booths or prison cells. For the structure and functionality, this contribution points to Untermann, who has described German town halls extensively (Untermann, 2009, 203-208).

Most of the mediaeval town halls of Mecklenburg were destroyed during the town fires of the 17th and 18th centuries. The oldest town halls of Parchim (14th C.), Gadebusch (1340), Wismar (13th C.), and Rostock (13th C.) (Schröder, 2002) are the only buildings of their kind with a mainly mediaeval core. Nevertheless, even though more than most town halls of the region are of baroque or

Figure 4. Historic town plan of Güstrow showing the market and church separated by the town hall. Illustration by Matthäus Merian the Elder, dated 1653: 1 = town hall, 2 = market square, 3 = churchyard.

19th-century origin, their spatial position mostly reflects their mediaeval position, allowing conclusions on the spatial relation between market share and town hall. In addition, archaeological excavations of the last 40 years have unveiled both the position and structure of a number of town halls that perished with time (Hoffmann, 2005, 179-190, Wiczorek, 2005, 191-192, Darjes and Schmidt, 2013, 106-117, Konczak, 2012, 162-173, Jänicke, 2012, 174-181, Konze and Rütz, 2008, 141-164).

A number of towns had town halls placed centrally in the market square. At the same time, the town hall was seldom placed solitary, but was most frequently the core of an agglomeration of buildings containing market stalls, the weight, a kaufhaus, a courthouse or bread or meat banks (Fig 4). Centrally placed town halls are prominently visible in Demmin, Penzlin, Malchin, and Friedland (Fig 5).

The most frequently used placement of the town hall in the towns of Mecklenburg is without doubt a free-standing peripheral location. Here the town hall is exposed prominently on one side of the market while standing solitary or in close agglomeration with buildings with market-related functions, such as stalls, the pharmacy or legal offices. This arrangement can, for example, be observed in Woldegk, Wismar or Güstrow (Fig. 4).

Finally, in a small number of cases, the town hall is located on a plot of a neighbouring block, as can be observed in Plau or Rostock. In Rostock, while the old town hall of the middle town was placed free-standing on the Neumarkt, the 14th-century new town hall of the united town was placed in two existing townhouses, which explains this unusual arrangement. The now prominent facade of the building is the result of later additions, famously illustrated by Gruber (Gruber, 1943).

Plot formations

The blocks of the urban towns consist of a number of more or less rectangular burgage plots (Hofstätten) which were situated with their short side towards the street. Plots situated in a corner of the block face their short side mostly to the main street. The hierarchy of streets inside the town can therefore

Figure 5. Friedlands Baroque town hall, perished in 1945, is prominent example of a centrally placed town hall. See also plan in Fig. 3. Source: www.ortschroniken-mv.de/images/c/c8/026b.jpg.

be recognised when analysing its plot plan (Kaspar, 2004). Already Schwinekörper points to the problem of the presumption of cadastral continuity from the Middle Ages to the Urkataster maps of the 19th century, which does not account for plot divisions or amalgamations, not to mention the great number of realignments after the urban fires of the 17th and 18th centuries (Schwinekörper, 1980). In Mecklenburg, the plot structure of a number of towns has been redrawn after major disasters (Boizenburg, 1709 and Grabow, 1725) or ducal intervention (Dömitz, 1554).

Nevertheless, archaeological evidence points to the fact that the mediaeval plot structure is largely intact in a number of towns in Mecklenburg, such as Woldegk and Friedland (Jänicke, 2003). Whether this fact is owed to the long period of economic stagnation between the 17th and the 19th centuries, or if other factors are relevant, will have to be the subject to further research. This study has therefore found it relevant to analyse the current plot structure in selected towns, regardless of knowledge about their factual age.

The front sides of the plots are in most towns directed to the market square, underlining its significance and economic value for neighbouring plot holders. In a few cases, corner plots at crossing main streets are directed towards the street (Gnoien, Neustadt, Parchim Neustadt, Stargard). These cases are limited to streets, leading to one of the town gates.

Measurements of plot widths were conducted in selected towns to establish if plots towards the market square differ in geometry from plots directed towards streets connecting the market and the main town gates. These measurements were conducted in 4 towns with inconclusive results (Fig. 6). Market plots in Woldegk are slightly larger than plots along the main streets, while they have the same width in Gnoien and Friedland. In Ribnitz, market plots are less wide than street plots of the main E-W road crossing through the town.

The value of the conducted measurements is low due to the poor statistical validity of the small number of plots around the market and the already mentioned question about the historic value of the maps used.

While the great majority of burgage plots in the towns of Mecklenburg are arranged in double rows, allowing entrance from parallel streets onto each plot, plot formations around marketplaces in many cases show single rows of plots accessible from both the market square and a parallel street.

Town	Market, average width of plots (m)	Number of registered plots	Main streets, average width of plots (m)	Number of registered plots
Friedland S: Urkataster 1904	13.3	20	12.9	170
Ribnitz Source: Cadastral map 2019	10.2	16	12.2	60
Gnoien Source: Cadastral map 2019	10.7	13	10.3	58
Woldegk S: Urkataster of 1955	15.2	7	13.7	63

Figure 6. Width of burgage plots at markets and main streets in 4 towns of Mecklenburg. Measurements conducted by the author.

These single-row blocks can be observed both in rectangular and non-rectangular geometries, for example, in Wittenburg, Wismar and Malchin (Fig. 8).

In Malchin, the function of the buildings in the single plot block has been clearly identified as a kaufhaus, or cloth hall (Wieczorek, 1996). In Ribnitz, the plot row dividing the market and church was occupied by the Latin school and the sacristan's house. In Wismar the rows on the eastern, northern and western sides of the market are occupied with single towns of plots. They have in common that the plot geometry is less deep (Ribnitz 10-12 m, Malchin 15 m, and Wismar 12-30 metres) and that they are or were covered with buildings in their entirety.

Building types related to the market square

A great number of market excavations around have, since the 1990s, revealed a wide number of building types occupying the area of modern market squares. Besides the town hall and kaufhaus, or burgage plots built in stone, a great variety of buildings has been documented. Many of the buildings related to market functions were built of wood. The excavation on Wismar's market revealed about 280 postholes (Schäfer, 2008), documenting a great variety of temporary buildings, banks or booths.

Archaeological excavations conducted by Wieczorek in Demmin give further insight into the structure and origin of building structures on mediaeval market squares (Wieczorek 2005). The excavations in the early 2000s followed the attempted cancellation of the town by Soviet troops in May 1945, recovering the cellars and foundations of the mediaeval town hall and its commenced but never finished eastern wing (Fig. 8). South of the town hall in a parallel row only 3 metres away, a number of market stalls were erected in the 13th century. Postholes reveal a construction based on two sill plates and vertical posts, suggesting a half-timbered house. These findings are reflected in a number of similar small half-timbered stalls found in the archaeological records of the markets of Strassburg, Ueckermünde and Pasewalk (Hoffmann, 2005, 181-187).

A second row of market stalls was situated 12 metres south of the town hall. Its construction is dated to the 14th century. This second row was erected on rectangular stone cellars with stairs on its southern facade. According to Wieczorek, the southern row of stalls might have replaced the wooden row standing close to the town hall. The southern row of cellars is documented over a length of 45 metres, probably creating the southern limit of the mediaeval market square. Its geometry and

Figure 7. Rows of single plots are frequently observed in the vicinity of mediaeval market squares: Wittenburg (1), in Wismar as rows of merchant houses on three sides of the square (2), and Malchin as a kaufhaus (3) on the eastern perimeter. Illustration by the author based on 2019-cadastral maps.

placement are similar to the previously described single-row plot formations in Wismar and other locations. They help to explain the genesis of single-row wooden stalls, of which some over time become signified as merchant houses, creating single-line plot formations accompanying market squares (Fig. 9).

The spatial organisation of mediaeval market squares changed during the early modern period. A number of town fires, documented in the archaeological records, destroyed wooden constructions which were not rebuilt during the 17th and 18th centuries. In Demmin, the fire of 1495 sparked the reorganisation of the urban space. The Merian illustration created about 1650 shows only a rectangular square with the solitary town hall at its centre. This development is significant for the evolution of urban communities beginning from the end of the 16th century, leading to the urban form documented in the cadastral maps of the 19th and early 20th centuries.

Conclusion

Our understanding of the spatial constitution of the mediaeval towns of eastern Central Europe is defined by the cadastral maps of the 19th century. A great deal of morphological research, such as Scheffel and Deppe (Scheffel, 2005 and Deppe, 1996), has been based on the assumption that they represent an approximate similarity with the physical reality of the 13th and 14th centuries. The archaeological excavations on market squares since 1990 are describing a radically different spatial composition of the market in the Middle Ages. Not only was its surface covered with a number of temporary buildings made of wood, but also is its outer perimeter the result of a transformation process, where some wooden market stalls were stonified into single rows of merchant houses surrounding the square, while others disappeared during a period of urban fires beginning at the end of the 16th century.

Further, the archaeological excavations of the last 30 years have contributed to a more accurate depiction of the relation between the market square, town hall and parochial church in towns like Ribnitz, Wittenburg and Penzlin. This knowledge is a valuable contribution to the ongoing spatial renewal process in small urban communities, where vanished town halls and other buildings related to the market are rebuilt or reconstructed by modern architecture, such as Demmin, Malchin or Woldegk.

In general, further morphological research on the urban structures of small towns with mediaeval origins will rely heavily on the archaeological records to complete and correct the data recovered from cadastral maps. This effort will contribute to improving knowledge in the debate on how the future of these communities can be formed by harvesting motives and narratives of their mediaeval past.

Figure 8. Demmin. The plan of the excavations on the market square reveals the town hall, perished in 1945, and two single rows of market stalls to the south. The row of wooden structures date to the 13th century; the row of stone structures to the 14th century. Illustration is based on Wiczorek 1998.

Notes

In memory of Prof. Monika Adamska, who inspired this research.

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Figure 9. Evolution of the market stall from simple wooden meat-, fish-, or bread-banks to wooden stalls, and merchant houses made of stone, placed on single line plots. Illustration by the author.